

POLICY PATHWAYS TOWARDS POVERTY REDUCTION IN THE MIDST OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC IN AFRICA: THE CASE OF NIGERIA AND DEMOCRATIC REPUBLIC OF CONGO (DRC).

By

Oaikhena Igbelokoto Marvellous, Ph.D
Department of Public Administration
College of Management and Social Sciences
Samuel Adegboyega University, Ogwa
Edo State, Nigeria
prince_marv12@yahoo.ca

Abstract

Africa has been bedeviled with poverty. The rate of poor people in Africa is alarming, compared to the availability of natural resources at the disposal of most states in Africa. Poverty has led to disconnect in families and friends. This phenomenon has brought about lack of confidence, malnutrition and other various kinds of diseases in most states in Africa. Sustainable policies had not been adequately implemented were they are initiated or pronounced. The Covid-19 pandemic, which has ravaged most countries in the world has further exposed the weaknesses of African countries Two countries in Africa were examined by the researcher. These are, Nigeria, and Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC). This study took a cursory look at some major challenges of policies and programmes initiated to address poverty in the two countries. It sought to know the positive correlation between educational attainment, level of income and occupational status in the countries, as these are expected strategies to aid reduction of poverty. The study adopted the qualitative method, as empirical literatures were sought, in order to ascertain the level of poverty and process or measures put in place to aid poverty reduction in the midst of the pandemic. The study, suggested a complete focus on knowledge attainment and skills development as some of the most important pathways to reducing poverty in Africa. As a result the social protection theory was adopted as a phenomenon towards the reduction of poverty in the two countries mentioned in the study. In other words, the promotion of a prosperous Africa is based on inclusive and sustainable development where development is people-driven, thus relying on the potential of Africans, especially its women and youths.

Key word: Poverty Reduction, Sustainable Policies, Programmes Development, Covid-19 Pandemic.

Introduction

Africa seem to have suffered one form of neglect from another, most especially from the international communities, or perhaps they have been taken advantage of, due to dependence, as the conditions have been exacerbated by governments of the industrialized nations as well as international agencies, perhaps unintentionally. Thus, the promotion of international “good will” in an attempt to

alleviate the shortage of savings in Africa, thereby granting credit facilities at low interest rates and easy repayment systems. This could be the reason why Ahiakpor (1994) asserted that, loans are meant to fill the so-called foreign-exchange gap, incorrectly believed to be responsible for the countries inability to import enough raw materials to increase capacity utilization in industrial production.

However, the anticipated neglect of Africa has potential benefits for Africans that are seldom discussed. The benefits include (a) a much better functioning of their economies; (b) escaping from further international indebtedness at the governmental level; and (c) relief from their countries being used as proxies.

The neglect of most Africa countries cannot be overemphasized. In a recent publication by Aljazeera on 10th of June, 2020, it reported that the, Norwegian Refugee Council (NRC), said two, out of ten African countries top the list of countries displaced and neglected due to crisis. Cameroon was the first, closely followed by Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC); Nigeria was said to be at the eight, position on the list. The Norwegian Refugee Council (NRC) ranks countries based on three criteria: Lack of political will on both the part of in-state and international actors; lack of media attention; and lack of international aid. This could be the reason why poverty has continued to pervade the Africa continent as adequate policies and programmes are not implemented to deal with the menace. More so the advent of the Covid-19 pandemic which was confirmed to have spread in Africa on the 14th of February, 2020, has posed serious challenge and set back in Africa, thereby worsening the already bad situation in the area of poverty and malnutrition, hindering the implementation of policies and programmes geared towards poverty reduction. Oaikhena and Osemeke (2016), asserted that policies are programmes the government set aside to address teething issues in the society.

Accordingly, the poverty headcount rate in Nigeria as at 2019 indicated that an individual is considered poor when he has an availability of less than 137.4 thousand naira (roughly 361 US dollars) per year, which implies that, a total of 40.1 percent of the population in Nigeria is living in poverty (Simona, 2020). It is however hoped that, by 2030, Africa will reduce the ranks of its extremely poor by 45 million and relative poverty will decline from 33.5 percent to 24 percent (Kristofer and Baldwin, 2019). Statistics in 2021, shows that Nigeria has the largest population in Africa with a total of 206 million individuals and DRC with 89 million people. Accordingly, Africa is said to be the second most populous continent in the world, after Asia, as it records the highest growth rate worldwide, with figures rising by over two percent every year.

Meanwhile, it has also been reported that in 2018, 72% of the population, especially in the North West and Kasai regions in DRC, was living in extreme poverty or less than \$1.90 a day (worldbank group.org., 2018). It further stated that, women and girls most especially, face systemic discrimination and ostracism. As a result, the United Nations (UN) consistently scores DR Congo as one of the lowest in terms of gender equality. According to Mutame (2005), he quoted Dr. Farkhonda Hassan, chair of the UN Economic Commission for Africa's Committee on Women and Development that despite achievements and progress made, African women face major challenges and obstacles. For example, she said, that the primary development policies in many countries, known as poverty reduction strategies, still do not take into account differences in income and power between men and women, hampering efforts to finance programmes that reduce inequality. Thus, the lack of formal economic opportunities, combined with the legacy of entrenched political conflicts and instability, as well as the rise of Covid-19 pandemic, high rates of malnutrition, illness, and poor education, poses many challenges on the African continent.

This study brings to bear the recent advent of Covid-19 pandemic, which has further made African countries more vulnerable, as it resulted in the sharp increase in poverty. If adequate measures

are not put in place, the pandemic could push Africa countries away from sustainable development programmes (SDG) organized by the United Nations, which targets the eradication of poverty by 2030. Jerving (2020) posited that, two of the continent's most populous countries, Nigeria and the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC), could see the largest increases in people entering extreme poverty. As Nigeria could see an increase of 8.5 million to 11.5 million and DRC could see an increase of 2.7 million to 3.4 million people. Which means that about 60% of the people newly entering extreme poverty were expected to live in West and Central Africa, hence progress has been limited in many African countries as they seek ways to overcome poverty through various policies.

Need for Sustainable Policies Towards Poverty Reduction in Africa

One major sustainable policy/programme geared towards poverty reduction in Africa, is the Agricultural programme. Many Africa Governments agree that, economic development through agriculture is a veritable tool for the reduction of poverty among Africans. Ghanaian President John Kufuor (served as president from 7th January 2001 to 7th January 2009) told Africans and international officials during a farm experts meeting in Accra that “the sad truth is that Africa does not seem to have the know-how to let this happen, and the agricultural sectors are inadequately supported” (Mutume, 2005). Improvement of Agricultural policies to address poverty in Africa cannot be overemphasized. As it is reported that 23 out of the 28 world poorest countries are found in Africa, considering the fact that, by 2030 (9 years from now) the Sustainable Development Goal Programmes shall end. This Goal had played a significant improvement in poverty reduction in the world since year 2000, when it was adopted. According to Asadullah (2019), the implementation of antipoverty programmes and poverty reduction strategies in individual countries became a routine part of national development plans, but, that there was considerable disparity in how different countries responded to the development goals as well as in their capacity to implement these plans.

As a result fighting poverty requires direct policy interventions. Considering the fact that African countries are less effective in reaching their poor citizens. The governments in sub-Saharan Africa for example do not have enough data and administrative knowledge, necessary for reliably identifying the poor in the society, which means the countries can't target resources allocated to them. Succinctly, many poor household in countries like Malawi, Mali, Niger and Nigeria, miss anti-poverty programmes, as the poorest households might not be easily reached. This is why the study advocated for social protection programme in response to poverty reduction.

Social protection has been defined by the United Nations in 2001 to be “the set of public and private policies and programmes undertaken by societies in response to various contingencies to offset the absence or substantial reduction of income from work; to provide assistance for families with children as well as provide people with health care and housing (Taylor, 2008; UN, 2001). Therefore, social protection expenditure has a prominent role in reducing and preventing poverty, containing inequality and addressing social exclusion. Particularly crucial is its capacity to ensure that people can escape poverty for good most especially in Africa. The risk of falling back into poverty is quite high, where effective social protection mechanisms do not exist. Social protection is thus essential in addressing not only monetary poverty but also social exclusion.

Social Protection As Pathway for Poverty Reduction in Africa

Social protection constitutes one of the essential channels through which governments can distribute and redistribute income and resources, and share the benefits of growth, reinforcing the democratic mandates granted them on election to fulfill societal expectations in Africa. The key role of

social protection in inclusive growth is now widely recognized in both Africa and Europe. It is therefore not surprising that higher levels of social protection expenditures are associated with lower levels of poverty. This poverty is exaggerated by the awareness, made possible by modern communication systems, that other societies enjoy great wealth and luxurious life styles. Accordingly, Africa feel an urgent need to succeed economically.

Solidar (2016) reported that, the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) is emerging from decades of brutal conflict which have devastated the country and hindered development. In recent years, with the emergence of a tenuous peace, efforts are being focused on rebuilding and stabilizing the state, building institutions and infrastructure and promoting economic growth. Social protection is now on the agenda, with the drafting of the 2015 National Social Protection Policy. The policy recognizes the role of social protection in enabling individuals to face risks and to guarantee them a minimum income allowing their integration into society.

According to Rodney (2005), it is clearly a rough approximation of the first attempt at exchange of a people coming into contact with strangers, and it was not a permanent procedure. One would have argued therefore, that the more strangers are involved in the development of a nation, the better for it. Africa has been at the receiving end of suffering and maladministration, right from the days of slavery till the present days of poverty associated with neglect. Thus, the restriction of national planning efforts towards economic development, only with scant reference to social, political and cultural development is often times recorded in Africa. This is also true when it comes to the organization of nations, as there must be elite among nations, which means national will are not equal. Besides serving as tool for directing the economy, the corporate state elite are the primary means by which the state controlled its citizens in Africa.

The case of Democratic Republic of Congo is of paramount interest, as the country is said to be unstable. According to the European humanitarian aid for Africa, the region hosts more than 526,000 refugees mainly from Rwanda, the Central African Republic, South Sudan, and Burundi. Hence the policies in the country have integrated different components of human security in practice. These policies have had mixed success. European Union strategies have not yielded the desired results as it has not been able to reverse existing governance conditions and practices; and have also not focused on structurally changing the extractive character of the political and administrative system of the DR Congo. According to Vlassenroot and Valerie (2016), they asserted that decades of patrimonial rule and economic mismanagement, and international and local pressure for democracy in the early 1990s, caused a deep political crisis and the near collapse of the Mobutu regime (1965-1997).

Notwithstanding, as the global poverty narrative shifts towards Africa, it seems obvious that ending extreme poverty by 2030 is almost impossible. However, it is important to note that the continent has turned the corner and poverty levels could come down substantially over the next decade, if adequate policies and programmes are implemented.

Intervention Programmes Toward Poverty Reduction In Africa

The world largest frontier today is Africa. According to Hamel, Tong and Hofer (2019), 422 million people lives below the global poverty line. This, they said, represents more than 70 percent of the world's poorest people. Nigeria and the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC) had posed a significant challenge for poverty reducing in the Africa continent. These two countries put together, are put at 150 million poor people who unfortunately, represent more than one-quarter of the total poverty population in Africa. This number is expected to increase representing almost half of Africa's poor population by 2030.

Though, Nigeria has promised to lift nearly 10 million people, up to the middle class/beyond over the next decade out of poverty. As a result relative poverty shares will decrease by almost three percent. Notwithstanding the number of poor people in Nigeria might still increase by some 20 million due to rapid population growth and lack of birth control. Meanwhile, in the Democratic Republic of Congo, relative poverty is projected to drop by as much as 15 percent but the absolute number might increase by almost 2 million, meaning over half the population would still be living in extreme poverty by 2030. Citizens are assured by respective government of their role in enhancing standard of living as they participate in programmes to ensure that achievement of set out goals to deal with the issue of poverty is achieved.

In order to achieve these goals, there is the need to continually promote programmes of interest which would aid Africans quick removal from the poverty line and address the issue of health care, especially the Covid-19 pandemic. Although programmes have been initiated and successfully implemented, the poverty rate in Africa remains significant despite measures put in place to address economic growth and reduce exploitation of the citizens. According to Roemer (1988), he expanded the theory of exploitation, by describing it as a sense of unequal access to the means of production by the non-propertied class, disenfranchised people, the unemployed, as the wage-workers suffer from injustice and exploitation.

One of the most recently introduced programme by the Nigeria government, is the National Youth Insurance Fund (NYIF), which was introduced in 2020. This programme was designed to provide opportunities for the teeming youths towards the alleviation of poverty and to cushion the effect of Covid-19 pandemic on most vulnerable and to help sustain Micro Small Medium Enterprise (MSMEs) in the country. Other initiatives includes: N-POWER (which is said to have engaged more than 500,000 beneficiaries; N-TECH and N-AGRO respectively (for youth training); FARMERMONI, TRADERMONI and MARKETMONI (for farmers, traders and youth empowerment); Digital Youth Nigeria was also initiated to implement skill acquisition programme, etc. The fight against poverty is one of the key components of the development of any country. If the percentage of poor people is high, national development slows down. Therefore, poverty alleviation programmes in Africa are extremely important, as these programmes are aimed at improving the economic and social conditions of the unprotected parts of the population. But the nature of poverty alleviation programme for implementation by donor agencies or European Unions, are often times questionable, as political connotation served as an important threat to the success of a programme. This could be the reason why Ikelegbe (2006) asserted that in some cases policy initiatives are offered or out-rightly dictated by international organizations and agencies such as International Monetary Fund (IMF), World Bank, etc.

In contrast, the Democratic Republic of Congo has ratified a number of international agreements relating to social protection, including parts of ILO Convention 102 on Social Security, and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights. Moreover, by adopting the ILO Recommendation on National Floors of Social Protection (R 202) the country is engaged in the set-up of a national floor of social protection for all its residents with the aim of building a comprehensive and human rights-based national social protection system. Currently, there are significant challenges to achieving universal social protection in DRC, to address these it will require support from the developed community (Solidar, 2016).

Addressing Poverty Reduction in Africa amidst Covid-19

The recent outbreak of the Corona virus pandemic has exposed some African countries to true dependence on the international communities for survival. As independence approached in most Africa countries, the appeal had to shift from how a foreign power should deal with the people to how the people should deal with their own affairs. It was necessary therefore, to shift gear from the rhetoric of the campaigns against colonialism to the argument of discipline, efficiency and probity in the conduct of public affairs in Africa. Rodney (2005), opined that the combination of being oppressed, being exploited, and being disregarded is best illustrated by the patterns of the economic infrastructure of Africa colonies, notably their roads and railways. Africans had the collective responsibility of redeeming the world, as they had to create an African nationality, a state strong enough to be the reservoir of humanity, the last citadel of freedom.

Perhaps the greatest threat to Africa is the role of influence organization in political affairs. With annual revenues larger than the national budget or even the gross national product of many Africa countries in which they do business; as they often operate without meaningful legal restraints, protected mainly by their structure and wealth. It therefore becomes imperative for African countries to balance growth and health care in the economy for both strong and sustainable will which is required to stimulate domestic trade and reduce poverty in the land, including the issue of ill-health. This could be the reason why Enofe, Ibeh and Ishola (2013), posited that, “.....events took place in various economies relating to the need for government to promote welfare (like social security), assist economically and socially disadvantaged people, combat private sector excesses – like the production of harmful goods, provide public goods, social amenities and infrastructure”.

It therefore means that Africa needs to reposition itself, in order to address the issue of health care and poverty. The distribution of goods for domestic market in various states in Africa is presently conducted through a network of intermediary traders, who essentially extend the distribution areas across different markets around Africa countries. Succinctly, improving the functioning of domestic markets and endorsing an overall domestic trade policy, would be able to fully harness the skills of its citizens and natural resources, which would play an important role in driving domestic trade, building health care facilities within Africa and outside Africa, and of course promote a synergy among traders and health care providers in African countries.

Theoretical Framework of Analysis

Social Protection Theory

Social protection, is defined by the United Nations Research Institute for Social Development, as concerned with preventing, managing, and overcoming situations that adversely affect people's well-being (UNRISD, 2010). Social protection has long been a domestic concern of wealthy nations, which have developed sophisticated institutions in order to protect their citizens against risk and provide assistance to the less privileged. Social protection has however been largely neglected, or addressed only with inappropriate tools, in majority of poor countries especially in Africa, where emphasis has been placed on economic growth. Donor agencies during the last decade, has seen an increasing emphasis on working holistically with African countries, within the full range of issues of concern to public policy. This has been initiated through public budget and development in general, in order to achieve sustainable reductions in poverty. The use of tax funded transfers to assist the poorest requires very high levels of support within society to be politically sustainable; these are among the greatest challenges that systems of democratic government face (Norton, Conway and Foster, 2001).

New approaches such as the Comprehensive Development Framework (CDF), or the development of over-arching Poverty Reduction Strategy Papers (PRSP) are part of debt relief processes, required to balance the understanding of public policy across all fields. An understanding of the policy field of social protection is necessary, in order to arrive at decisions about the appropriate overall mix of policies at the national level. This invariably means that, social protection consists of policies and programs designed to reduce poverty and vulnerability by promoting efficient labour markets, diminishing people's exposure to risks, and enhancing their capacity to manage economic and social risks, such as unemployment, exclusion, sickness, disability, and old age (world bank, 2001).

Social protection has become one of the processes by the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal, aimed at promoting greater equality amongst states. Traditionally, social protection has been used in the European welfare state and other parts of the developed world to maintain a certain living standard, and address transient poverty (UNRISD, 2010). Thus poverty is the target for social protection mechanism. Moreover, it is designed to lift recipients out of poverty, rather than exclusively providing passive protection against contingencies (UNRISD, 2010). It has rapidly been used in trying to reduce and ultimately eliminate poverty and suffering in developing countries (mostly in Africa), in order to enhance and promote economic and social growth.

Poverty Eradication Using Technology

At any given time, the data on the available resources, i.e. human, material and agricultural are defined by the available technology. The technological frontier shifts, as knowledge accumulates and become diffused; the process of deepening and widening the frontier throws up new possibilities for men in the mastery of nature. Combinations of resources that might have appeared remote today may become relevant tomorrow in the light of new technological developments. Thus justifying state interventions in the economy of Africa was not only an ideological necessity, but also a historical one. It is necessary that Africa states should consolidate in this innovative drive. This could be the reason why Herbst (2000), posited that, state consolidation, which came into vogue in the immediate post-independence era, emanated from the underlying assumption that the state was a major means to bring about social change and fulfilling economic and social aspirations with strong integrative and development objectives.

Therefore, in order to enhance economic and health care development in Africa, effective measurement is preferred and more emphasize in public policy programmes where the issues of goal attainment is quite important. The society usually wants to know how much of desired and enunciated policy goals are being achieved through implementation. According to Ikelegbe (2006), the citizenry are the consumers of public policy programme services, as policies are made to resolve their problems and may actually have emanated from citizen pressure. Thus, people living in poverty and deprived health care should not be seen simply as targets or subjects of the various interventions, but rather they should be seen as active agents in the creation and application of these interventions. Their involvement helps ensure the relevance of the work. If the people are not carried along in the drive to eliminate poverty and diseases in the land, the social contract between the people and government suffers set-back. This is so because democracy had paved way for citizen's participation in governance through elections and adequate representatives.

As technology advance in these areas, so also the citizens acquire more knowledge in addressing salient issues that could lead to the eradication of poverty, malnutrition disease, and the reintroduction of policies and programmes that would enhance the living condition of the people. Hence such programmes are people driven. This point can be illustrated through the social protection perspectives as it appears to

be the main role to lifting the constraints of human and economic development posed by social risk, ensuring the satisfaction of basic needs, and implementing a rights-based approach to human development. Barrientos and Hulme (2009) quoted Munro (2008) as they said that competing perspectives on risks or needs or rights, support alternative views of what social protection seeks to achieve. As some of these achievements is to protect and prevent the people from deprivation, promote and transform social equality/empowerment of the citizenry, thereby enhancing economic growth and eliminating disease in the land.

Strategy To Poverty Reduction and Disease Management

Knowledge Attainment and Skills Development

In knowledge attainment to poverty reduction, and disease management, certain numbers of projects which appear to have been managed successfully to reach the poor and increase their incomes and productivity have become very necessary. As employability and productive capacity need to be linked to the provision of training and skills development, provision of health care. It is therefore very important to see the attainment of education and training system geared towards skills development and social-economic growth. The structural adjustment policies of the 1980s which focused its attention on poverty reduction in Africa had human face, as it targeted the poor and vulnerable in the society. This could be the reason why King and Palmer (2006) posits that, the poverty focus of what may be called the world's development agenda and its targeting of minimal goals for social development in primary education, gender equality, basic health care and family planning have led to a major preoccupation of the development community with service delivery rather than with growth, productive capacity, or with wider development policy frameworks.

Thus, poverty in Africa is the problem of bad government that has the weakest civil societies, which negatively affects the quality and transparency of the state and its institutions, while the rich countries can often afford bad or incompetent governments. In Africa, bad government can destroy any prospect for economic liftoff. According to Norton, Conway and Foster (2001), they said that, social protection policy is also intimately connected to debates on social cohesion and social exclusion. This they said reflects a view in the social sciences which emphasizes that inclusion is collective, as it provides for mutual assistance centrally to the definition of social life. To look at this relationship from a different angle, when a collectivity such as the state loses the capacity to provide for the needs of its members (citizens) in a crisis, like the pandemic, it suffers a crisis of legitimacy as a consequence, and accordingly finds it harder to govern. Good and effective governance that is knowledge driven is therefore sacrosanct to the reduction of poverty and disease in Africa.

Level of Income and Educational Status

One unique strategy in poverty and diseases reduction in Africa that should be sustained has to do with the level of education and income earned by individuals in the society, if there is a genuine effort to eradicate or minimize poverty and diseases in other to ensure sustainable livelihoods. It is imperative to integrate strategies to deal with eradicating poverty and implementing adequate policies geared towards equitable distribution of resources, wealth and income that could easily lead to social protection coverage. This strategy will eradicate hunger and malnutrition. According to Abdullah and Inaba (2020), they asserted that poverty reduction in developing regions is slowing because of the prevailing nature of extreme income inequality, which is considered a powerful threat to economic progress.

The Democratic Republic of Congo is one of the poorest countries in Africa with the citizens earning an average of \$394.25 per year; thanks to good coordination in monetary and budget policies, the inflation rate, which reached 29.3% in 2018, fell to 4.5% in 2019. It has been asserted that the current account deficit would most likely worsen in 2020 (to 4.6% of Gross Domestic Product) and 2021 (4.3% of Gross Domestic Product), and the fiscal balance would most likely remain in the red (0.2% of GDP in 2020 and 0.3% in 2021), partly from financing the free education policy (African Economic Outlook, 2020).

While in Nigeria the severe cuts in public spending following the recession have affected governance nationwide. The situation in the education sector, has exacerbated existing problems. Ongoing student protests and strikes have rocked Nigerian universities for years including the recent ASSU strike that lasted for over Nine (9) months, this unfortunately, are symptoms of several underfunded higher education system in Nigeria.

Africa needs to realize its full potentials. Zimako (1999), had said that, Nigeria has since independence in 1960, woefully, regrettably, ashamedly and painfully failed to give supposed leadership to Africa (and the developing world) in manifesting best democratic processes, and while she crawls in this regard, she has been overtaken by more serious and democratic-conscious nations like South Africa, Ghana and Benin Republic

Summary/Conclusion

Nigeria is a diverse multiethnic country with more than 520 spoken languages. English is the official language, Hausa, Yoruba and Igbo are also major languages in the country; while the Democratic Republic of Congo is the second largest country in Africa. The people of the DRC represent over 200 ethnic groups, with nearly 250 languages and dialects spoken throughout the country. The DRC is among the most resource-rich countries on the planet, with an abundance of gold, tantalum, tungsten, and tin, all minerals used in electronics such as cell phones and laptops, yet it continues to have an extremely poor population.

This study conceptualized the pathway towards the eradication of poverty and diseases in Africa especially in Nigeria and Democratic Republic of Congo, both in West Africa in the midst of the pandemic. The pandemic has spread to most parts of the continents unfortunately, with the possible exception of Antarctica. However, Africa appears different when compared with other parts of the continents. Thus, the study revealed the further impoverishment of the people, as the study advocated the need for poverty reduction programmes with sincere implementation by relevant governmental agencies, most especially in the two countries under review. It also revealed that several poverty alleviation programmes had been introduced, but that lack of political will and insincerity in some cases among personnel in the two countries under review, had led to the ineffectiveness of the programmes and misplacement of priorities. It will be counter-productive if policies and programmes are not implemented to meet the yearnings of the people (Oaikhenana and Osemeke, 2016). The socio-political inclusion of the poor and vulnerable in the society, which ought to be an improvement of social security, and livelihood enhancement, coupled with activities, which includes promoting opportunities for socio-economic growth, facilitating gender empowerment, and improving health care facilities are most times neglected.

As a result, poverty and diseases continues to be prevalent in Nigeria and Democratic Republic of Congo. Nigeria houses the largest population in Africa. Accordingly, Nigeria is said to be one of the countries with extremely fast growing population in the area of numbers. It is expected that in 2050, Nigeria might house almost 400 million people, thus becoming the third most populated country after

China and India. It is currently the seventh most populous country in the world, with a population of more than 200 million people. Thus the need for adequate social protection programmes geared towards the alleviation of poverty, unemployment and health care infrastructure, cannot be overemphasized.

Recommendations

In view of these, the study advocated for the promotion of the social protection programmes which is funded by national taxes, with some support from donors agencies, depending on the level of national resources available, is considered to be most appropriately to be delivered by the states, in order to enhance adequate development and aid the elimination of poverty, hunger and disease in Africa.

In other words adequate policies should be developed towards the eradication of poverty in Africa, as the Covid-19 pandemic is here to stay. There should be improvement to access in the areas of health care, sustainable livelihoods, entrepreneurial skill development opportunities and the provision of productive resources; support systems must be provided for those who cannot support themselves; empowerment must be considered; and international donor agencies should be encouraged to work directly within poverty or diseases prone environment in Africa thereby providing social protection.

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